

Logistics solutions for mountain areas: A patent analysis

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Abstract

Mountain regions, characterized by harsh weather and complex terrains, present significant logistics and transportation challenges. Overcoming these challenges necessitates specialized expertise and advanced technologies. Using a machine learning algorithm called Latent Dirichlet Allocation on patent documents, this study seeks to unveil the current development state of the field. The analysis reveals twelve discernible clusters representing distinct specialized areas, including seat and suspension control systems, intelligent vehicle control systems, electric vehicles, bicycle frame design, and safety devices with future potential significance in the field. The findings contribute to the academic discourse in the logistics field and hold practical implications for stakeholders.

Keywords: Mountain logistics, patent analysis, topic modeling

Introduction

Mountain regions, characterized by elevated landforms and rugged terrain, encompass significant portions of the world's population and land area (Du, 2009). These zones have a profound impact on global ecosystems and economic development as they provide resources to downstream domains, support agriculture and industry, and offer recreational opportunities and cultural heritage significance to communities (Moretti et al., 2023). The preservation and sustainable development of mountain areas are therefore not only desirable but also essential for maintaining ecological balance and ensuring the well-being of both local communities and urban populations (Carroll-Foster and Li Pun, 1993; Moretti et al., 2023). In this regard, logistics and transportation play a crucial role, serving as essential drivers for the progress and growth of such territories.

However, mountain areas present unique challenges due to their steep slopes, valleys, harsh weather patterns, and complex geological features, which make logistics and transportation activities difficult (Jung & Kim, 2022). These challenges result in higher transport infrastructure costs, longer travel times, increased fuel consumption, elevated

risks of accidents, and limited accessibility to remote zones, thus hindering the movement of goods and passengers (Lu et al., 2021). For this reason, logistics and transportation patterns in these areas are distinct from those in plain settings and require tailored efforts to address the problems the terrain poses (Du, 2009).

Recent studies have illustrated the emergence of a wide array of solutions aimed at overcoming the aforementioned obstacles; examples include aerial ropeway transportation systems (Reichenbach & Puhe, 2018), unmanned aerial vehicles or drones (Holzmann et al., 2021), and cargo bicycles (Gonzalez-Calderon et al., 2022). Furthermore, in the era of Industry 4.0, the logistics industry is being transformed, with the aid of disruptive advancements such as big data (Lekic et al., 2020), the Internet of Things (IoT), cloud computing, artificial intelligence, and machine learning (Zhu et al., 2022) which are considered enablers in optimizing operations and improving efficiency.

Against this rapidly evolving context, scholars have highlighted the presence of unexplored domains (Reis et al., 2024) and a lack of comprehensive dashboards providing evidence of the actual development state of logistic solutions for mountain areas (Botín-Sanabria et al., 2022). This scenario poses at least three challenges. First, potential users often cannot identify the most suitable solution for their needs because of limited knowledge of the available options (Mejri et al., 2014). Second, policymakers lack an overall vision to inform actions targeted at supporting mountain logistics (Long et al., 2023). Third, organizations interested in advancing mountain technologies struggle to understand where to prioritize efforts due to uncertainty regarding the current progress (Fulzele & Shankar, 2022). Mapping the innovation landscape in mountain logistics and transportation is essential for decision-making and bridging the gap between expectations and reality (Abbas et al., 2014); it helps users stay updated on the latest technological advancements that improve efficiency, safety, and convenience in logistics and transportation. Additionally, it aids organizations in evaluating the competitiveness of different actors in mountain logistics and transportation technology, informing strategic planning and cooperation initiatives (Spitsberg et al., 2013).

An effective approach for gaining an overall picture of mountain logistics and transportation R&D arena involves conducting a patent analysis using machine learning techniques (Steyvers & Griffiths, 2007). On the one hand, machine learning tools enable the processing of vast amounts of data, identifying patterns and relationships that would be difficult or impossible to detect through traditional approaches (Qiu et al., 2016). On the other, patent documents represent a valuable data source that can provide information on real-world trends, technological interdependencies, and leading players, allowing for a detailed understanding of the issues at hand (Ercan & Kayakutlu, 2014). Patent analysis can also support intellectual property management strategies of organizations involved in mountain logistics and transportation, including licensing, technology transfer, and patent portfolio management (Spitsberg et al., 2013). Furthermore, understanding patent trends and activities helps policymakers formulate effective policies and regulations to support innovation and address challenges in mountain logistics and transportation (Albino et al., 2014).

Motivated by this background, we undertake an in-depth patent analysis that employs Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA) to provide a holistic view of technological trends and advancements in mountain logistics and transportation. The research answers the following question: What is the current state of technological development in mountain logistics and transportation?

The findings show twelve clusters representing distinct specialized areas within mountain transport vectors. Among them, the technological areas of seat and suspension control systems, intelligent vehicle control systems, electric vehicles, bicycle frame

design, and safety devices have potential significance in mountain logistics and transportation's future. Meanwhile, the fields of automotive body structures, mountain bike parts and accessories, and mechanical power transmission are reaching a state of saturation or becoming obsolete.

Data source and methodology

The study's methodology includes data extraction, processing, analysis, and presentation (see Figure 1). We utilized patent documents as the primary data source to achieve our goal due to their detailed information on innovations in specific technological domains (Singh et al., 2016). Then, we conducted LDA topic modeling to find the hidden, latent structure of technological areas within mountain logistics and transportation.

Data extraction and initial filtering

Patent data was collected from the Derwent Innovation Index database. To extract relevant patent documents for analysis, we used a combination of keywords and IPC codes (Kwon et al., 2022). Integrating keyword searches with IPC codes allows for refining search outcomes within a particular technological domain, ensuring the retrieval of more pertinent patents (Shalaby & Zadrozny, 2019). In this regard, we searched for relevant patent documents using the keyword “mountain*” combined with IPC classification codes for transportation (i.e., B60 — B68). The keywords were searched for in the titles, abstracts, and patent claims to ensure no relevant documents were missed during the analysis (Xie & Miyazaki, 2013).

The result gives a pool of 19,472 patent applications. According to researchers such as Ghaffari et al. (2023), the abstracts of patent documents contain the essential technical information and technology used in the invention. Therefore, the textual content in patent abstracts was considered for topic modeling analysis, and patents lacking abstracts were excluded. Furthermore, considering the growing focus on promoting sustainable development in mountain regions after the United Nations Conference on Environment and Development in 1992 (Carroll-Foster & Li Pun, 1993; Price & Kim, 1999), only patent applications between January 1992 and September 2023 (the search conducted) were selected to create our initial database, which results in 16,681 patents. Based on their respective IPC classification, the abstracts of the initial database were categorized, and sample abstracts were reviewed for each category to check their relevance. This allowed us to refine our sample and exclude certain IPC classifications unrelated to mountain transport vectors. The excluded classes were B63, which pertains to ships or other waterborne vessels and their related equipment; B65, which deals with conveying, packing, storing, and handling thin or filamentary material; B67, which is about opening or closing bottles and jars, or similar containers and liquid handling; and B68, which relates to saddlery and upholstery.

After filtering out the irrelevant patent documents, the final database consists of 7,084 patents.

Data processing and topic modeling

Text mining is valuable for detecting topics, clustering documents, and summarizing unstructured data (Hashimi et al., 2015). In this study, we used topic modeling to accurately categorize technological areas related to mountain logistics and transportation based on patent documents. The model used for topic modeling was LDA, which helped to ensure a reliable and valid thematic classification (Blei et al., 2003). The main challenge of performing LDA on textual data is appropriate processing to ensure high-quality results (Maier et al., 2018) by eliminating noisy texts. The process involves

tokenization, eliminating high-frequency stop-words irrelevant to the field, and removing custom stop-words. All characters are converted to lowercase, and numbers and special characters like punctuation are removed. Lemmatization is applied to get the precise part of speech and convey the intended meaning of a word within a sentence (Savin et al., 2022). Custom stop-words represent common terms in patent documents that create noise due to high frequency. These include (claims, mountain, provided, end, first, one, two, second, c, solved, copyright, jpo, also, least, side, like, fig, use, thereby, means, problem, comprising, side, part, portion, solved, said, solution). For more information on the methodological procedures and data processing, please refer to Figure 1.

Methodological steps	Activities performed	Results
Data collection	-- Patents on mountain logistics were collected. Database -- Derwent Innovation Patent Query -- Keyword Mountain* + IPC classification for transportation (B60-B68) Coverage -- Titles, Abstracts, Claims of patents	Initial patent documents = 19,472
Initial data filtering	-- Removing patents without abstracts -- Considering only patent applications between Jan 1992 and Sept. 2023 -- Excluding IPC classifications unrelated to mountain transport vectors	Remaining patent documents = 7,084
Data preprocessing	-- Lemmatize -- Removing non-letter characters -- Removing stop-words and common words -- Create a dictionary -- Create corpus	Cleaned textual data for LDA topic modeling
Topic Modeling	LDA on pre-processed texts from abstracts of patent documents. -- Train LDA model -- Apply the LDA model to generate topics	12 topics were found from the analysis
Content analysis	Thematic/Technological area identification -- Based on topic keywords & -- Reading sample patent abstracts	Emerging themes

Figure 1: Summary of methodological procedures adapted from Savin et al. (2022).

The relevant topics were extracted from the patent abstracts without relying on pre-existing knowledge or input to avoid bias (Maier et al., 2018). To this end, we used the "Gensim" software package in Python. Furthermore, the abstracts of patents were pre-processed using Python libraries, including "pandas," "openpyxl," "nltk," and "spacy." Another challenge in topic modeling is that the topics generated may be inconsistent or difficult to interpret (Maier et al., 2018). Additionally, determining the appropriate number of topics for a given corpus is a decision the user makes. To address these challenges, we changed the number of topics from two to fifteen and assessed the resulting coherence scores. The number of topics that provided the highest coherence values is twelve, with a score of 0.544 (see Figure 2), which aligns with previous studies

(e.g., Ghaffari et al., 2023). This rigorous approach allowed us to capture the nuanced topic structures inherent in patent documents, providing an in-depth assessment of the technological domains in mountain logistics and transportation.

Figure 2: Coherence score vs. number of topics

Results

Temporal distribution of patent applications

As shown in Figure 3, the analysis indicates a clear upward trend in patent applications related to mountain logistics and transportation, reaching a high record of 1,139 in 2020. Growth rates ranged from 0.35% in 1999 to 60.65% in 1997. The surge in patent applications can be attributed to three main factors. The first is the rising need for transportation means in mountain regions. Following the 1992 EU conference on mountain development, there has been a growing demand from mountaineers and tourists for more diverse, high-quality, and convenient travel options (Carroll-Foster & Li Pun, 1993). This has boosted innovation in logistics and transportation technology and services. Second, organizations are increasingly recognizing the pivotal role of patents in enhancing their market value, and nowadays they heavily rely on patents as crucial elements of their business strategies (Agostini et al., 2019). Third, the enhancement of digital technologies brings remarkable solutions for logistics and transportation challenges in mountain areas, such as intelligent vehicle control systems, autonomous vehicles, and electric vehicles, resulting in heightened R&D efforts (Barreto et al., 2017).

As a side note, the decrease in the number of publications in 2023 is due to the fact that patent applications are published 18 months after the earliest priority date (Ernst, 1999). To ensure we don't miss out on the latest advancements, we conducted our search up to 2023 and included available patents in the database.

Figure 3: Annual number of patents (1992 -- 2023)

Patent distribution by application country/region

The geographical distribution of patent applications for mountain logistics and transportation reveals the leading position from China (47% of the total), followed by Japan at 26% and Korea at 8%. The United States, Germany, and other countries (e.g., Canada, Austria, Russia, France) contribute to the remaining percentage (Figure 4). This result aligns with the current trend in patent applications. According to the 2020 report by the European Patent Office (EPO), there has been a decline in the number of patent applications from US and European companies, while there has been a consistent growth in the number of applications from companies in China and South Korea. More specifically, in 2022, China filled out more patent and utility model applications than the total applications filled out by the US and Japan (WIPO, 2023).

Figure 4: Share of patent applications by country (1992 -- 2023)

Additionally, we investigated the dominance of patent filing across different countries over time. Our analysis revealed a clear shift in patent filing dominance by country/region across three distinct periods: 1992-2001, 2002-2011, and 2012-2023. In the initial period (1992-2001), Japan emerged as the predominant contributor, accounting for 33.37% of the patents filed, followed by China at 21.92%. However, a notable shift occurred in the subsequent periods, with China progressively asserting dominance, reaching an impressive 67.88% of total patents filed by 2012-2023. After years of relative stability, the United States is experiencing a decrease in its presence, from 9.34% in the first period to 5.62% in the last. Interestingly, Germany and South Korea exhibited noteworthy variations in their positions, reflecting dynamic changes in global innovation patterns.

Extracting technology areas (topics) and content analysis

Using topic modeling, we identified twelve discernible clusters representing distinct specialized areas within mountain transport vectors (see Figure 5). For each cluster, an in-depth analysis of patenting activities was conducted to get a comprehensive overview of the technological landscape. Patent quality, which helps to assess innovations' potential technological and economic value, is measured using forward citation metrics (Squicciarini et al., 2013). In this regard, "seat and suspension control systems," "intelligent vehicle control systems," "electric vehicles and electrical systems," "bicycle frame design," and "safety devices" emerged as frontrunners, which have potential significance in the future of mountain transportation. Whereas the fields of "automotive body structures," "mountain bike parts and accessories," and "mechanical power

transmission" are receiving fewer citations, which suggests that these technological areas may be reaching a state of saturation or becoming obsolete.

Figure 5: Word cloud for topics in mountain logistics and transportation

In addition, the study shows the number of patent applications in each field, which helps to identify research and innovation trends in the examined technological area. This nuanced understanding of topic-specific patent activity provides an in-depth overview of the technological landscape and opens avenues for innovative solutions to enhance mountain transportation and logistics systems. The temporal trends of the twelve technological subcategories can assist policymakers and researchers in recognizing patterns, prioritizing areas of interest, and making informed strategic decisions regarding mountain logistics and transportation (Figure 6). Such classification of topics enriches the scholarly discourse on technological advancements, contributing to a more informed and targeted approach to fostering innovation within the given temporal context.

Figure 6: Temporal trends of the twelve technological subcategories (bubble size indicates the number of patent applications)

Conclusions

According to the findings and the considerations reported in the previous sections, our analysis is valuable to literature, practice, and policy. From an academic perspective, we present a comprehensive overview of technological advancements and innovation dynamics in the field of mountain logistics and transportation. This facilitates the consolidation of existing knowledge while aiding scholars in pinpointing areas where additional investigations can be conducted. Moreover, we emphasize the significance of using data-driven methods to analyze innovation-related dynamics. Lastly, we underscore the geopolitical nuances of technological progress, noting China's emphasis on public investment and Japan's reliance on private sector-driven innovation. This distinction marks an interesting aspect of study for innovation researchers, indicating the importance of delving into the impacts of different approaches—state-driven versus market-driven—on the speed and character of technological development.

From a practical point of view, we provide reliable and objective information that can guide strategic decision-making and foster innovation in mountain transportation vectors. In particular, we identify the critical technological areas that require further attention and investment while pointing out domains moving towards saturation and decline; this helps companies in direct their R&D efforts and facilitates strategic planning.

From a policy standpoint, our findings offer valuable insights to inform promotion and regulatory activities aimed at sustaining further innovation efforts. Specifically, despite Europe's extensive mountain terrain (Walsh, 2019), the participation of European organizations in the R&D landscape remains limited. This might suggest the enactment of incentives schemes (e.g., tax breaks, financial support) to foster the role of this region within the mountain logistics sector.

This article has some limitations that can be addressed in future research. Firstly, we relied on a keyword-based approach and IPC codes to extract patent data, which may have excluded some relevant patents that did not match the search criteria. Future contributions could use more comprehensive and sophisticated methods to collect patent data, such as natural language processing or machine learning techniques. Secondly, while the study used LDA to generate topics from patent abstracts, it may have overlooked important information in other parts of the patent documents, such as claims, specifications, or drawings. Future research could use more advanced topic modelling methods and include all sections of patent documents, to capture the complexity and evolution of the topics. Thirdly, we build on forward citation analysis and descriptive statistics to evaluate the quality and impact of the topics, thus neglecting aspects such as patent age, patent office, or patent examiner; future studies could use more robust and nuanced indicators. Lastly, we focused on the technological aspects of mountain logistics and transportation without considering their social, environmental, or economic implications. Future research could extend the analysis by combining different data sources, such as scientific publications, news articles, or social media posts, to gain a broader and deeper understanding of the field and its implications.

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